

LECHER'S DISULPHIDE FROM TETRAMETHYLTHIOCARBAMIDE.
CONSTITUTION OF 'FORMAMIDINE DISULPHIDE'

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The supposed disulphide oxidation product of tetramethylthiocarbamide has been shown to be derived from a single molecule of the latter. Its properties indicate structural analogy with "formamidine disulphide", the oxidation product of $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$.

By the oxidation of tetramethylthiocarbamide Lecher reported (*Annalen*, 1925, 445, 36, 51) formation of a disulphide (I) analogous to "formamidine disulphide", the oxidation product of thiocarbamide (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2166). Since a thiol form, conventionally necessary for disulphide formation on oxidation, is not possible by tautomerization in the case of tetramethylthiocarbamide, to explain disulphide formation,

Lecher assumed co-ordination of a H by the sulphur of this compound forming a potential $\ominus \oplus$ $-\text{S}^{\oplus} \text{H}^{\ominus}$ prior to oxidation. An ammonium type of structure was assigned to this compound on the lines of *S*-methyl derivative of tetramethylthiocarbamide (*loc. cit.*).

In view of the evidence of non-formation of disulphides from aromatic thiocarbamides (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 37) and author's work (*ibid.*, 1951, 28, 119) showing that 'formamidine disulphide' itself is probably built from a single molecule of thiocarbamide, it was of interest to re-examine the question of the constitution of 'disulphide' (I).

Following Lecher's procedure, as well as by the action of bromine and chlorine on tetramethylthiocarbamide in benzene or chloroform media, perchlorate, bromide and chloride of the 'disulphide' have been obtained. Behaviour of these salts towards iodine, potassium iodide, acids and alkalis is similar to 'formamidine disulphide' salts. But, they are in general stabler than the latter, and although they also 'hydrolyse' completely in an aqueous medium generating free acids, this change is comparatively slow and tends to be complete at much greater dilution. From these facts it is clear that the constitution of Lecher's 'disulphide' salts (I) and of 'formamidine disulphide' salts must be analogous (*vide* Sahasrabudhey this *issue*, p. 309), with such finer differences as could be explained by the presence of four methyl substituents in the former.

Molecular weight of the hydrobromide (I, where X is a Br) was determined by the freezing point method using glacial acetic acid. In three separate experiments it was found to be 206, 214 and 226 which values are in close agreement with 212 required for $(\text{CSN}_2\text{Me}_4)\text{Br}$. It is concluded therefore that Lecher's 'disulphide' oxidation product from tetramethylthiocarbamide is not a true disulphide

but has been formed from a single molecule of thiocarbamide. The great similarity of its properties with those of 'formamidine disulphide' suggests structural analogy with the latter (vide this issue p. 309); this is being examined separately.

Since the 'disulphide' can be obtained by the oxidation of the thiocarbamide with bromine or chlorine in a non-acidic, indifferent solvent medium, like benzene, it is evident that the formation of a -SH group by co-ordination of H⁺ does not precede oxidation as postulated by Lecher.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tetramethylthiocarbamide was prepared by the regulated decomposition of tetramethylthiuram [disulphide] by gradual heating up to 200° in a flask fitted with an air condenser. The reaction can be represented as .

The thiocarbamide was purified by crystallisation from water, m.p. 78°. (Found : N, 20.94; S, 24.0. CSN₂Me₄ requires N, 21.2; S, 24.24 per cent).

Preparation of Tetramethylformamidine Disulphide Salts

Perchlorate of the disulphide was prepared according to Lecher's procedure (*loc. cit.*). On slow crystallisation, large transparent, hexagonal plates were obtained which were found to answer the description given by Lecher.

Bromide.—Tetramethylthiocarbamide was dissolved in benzene and a benzene solution of bromine was gradually added. A white granular mass was initially precipitated which on addition of more bromine turned yellow and then red and finally dissolved giving a red solution. For the preparation of the hydrobromide, the addition of bromine was stopped as soon as the precipitate took a pale yellow colour. It was filtered out and to the filtrate more of the bromine solution was added when a further lot of precipitate was thrown down. By repeating this process a number of times, crude bromine derivative of the thiocarbamide was obtained. On standing it discharged its pale yellow colour and a white powder was left (cf. behaviour of the bromine-addition product of the thiocarbamide). This is the hydrobromide; it is easily soluble in water, alcohol and acetic acid, but is insoluble in benzene and chloroform. It was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 143-44°. (Found : Br, 37.5. CSN₂Me₄Br requires, Br, 37.73 per cent.)

Hydrochloride.—If instead of bromine a stream of chlorine is passed in benzene solution of the tetramethylthiocarbamide, a white precipitate is formed at first which redissolves on further passage of chlorine giving a pale yellow solution. The white precipitate is the crude hydrochloride; crystals from alcohol, m.p. 110°.

General Properties of the Salts.—The above salts are freely soluble in water but do not dissolve in organic solvents like benzene or chloroform. They are, however, soluble in alcohol and glacial acetic acid. Their aqueous solutions are strongly acidic

and the acidity can be titrated with alkali. The equivalent weight of the bromide and hydrochloride, so determined, agree within experimental limits with $\text{CSN}_2\text{Me}_4\text{Br}$ and $\text{CSN}_2\text{Me}_4\text{Cl}$, viz., 212 and 167.5. They liberate iodine from an aqueous solution of potassium iodide.

All these properties indicate close similarity with formamidine disulphide (salts). Influence of various factors *e.g.*, dilution, concentration of KI, addition of acids and the dielectric constant of the medium on its behaviour towards aqueous potassium iodide has been investigated in detail. There is an overall similarity with 'formamidine disulphide' salts. These results are being discussed separately.

Molecular Weight Determination

(i) 0.6700 g. of the bromide, dissolved in 20 c.c. glacial acetic acid, gave a depression of 0.50° which corresponds to 226.2.

(ii) To the above solution 10 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were added ; depression found 0.40° corresponds to 206.4.

(iii) 0.2548 g. of the bromide in 20 c.c. glacial acetic acid gave a depression of 0.22° which corresponds to 214.

(iv) 0.1458 g., dissolved in 20 c.c. glacial acetic acid, gave a depression of 0.15° which corresponds to 180.

On ageing of the solution low values were obtained indicating decomposition of the compound.

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